

Opinion

Plastic Pollution:

A GLOBAL CHALLENGE THAT CAN BE SOLVED

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What can we all do to limit plastic pollution? This question has been propelled to the forefront of public attention by an episode of Blue Planet II on the BBC. Perhaps even Sir David Attenborough did not expect the shocking images of seabirds badly injured or killed by plastic litter to impact so many viewers as much as they did. Environmental awareness increased vastly, however a recent study that directly tested the 'Blue Planet effect' suggests that people may have not changed their plastic-use behaviours much. The encouraging increase in awareness of the global plastic pollution plight has been years in the making, thanks to research and action by many scientists, volunteers, and NGOs. Such work has been giving some answers to the 'what can we do' question. In the past year, I worked as Research Manager for one of these committed NGOs, Earthwatch Europe. Here I will focus on macroplastics, i.e. plastics > 5mm long; these tend to be dominant in litter picks, with ten top10 items (Fig. 1: e.g. bags, bottles, and food wrappers) comprising 71% of the total number of litter items in eight studies in European aquatic ecosystems, mostly in the UK (Winton *et al.*, 2019).

As part of Earthwatch Europe's Plastic Rivers programme, my colleagues and I published a study on what consumers can do to reduce their plastic use. We explored the effectiveness of 27 plastic reduction actions to determine which ones may realistically have the most positive impact by

reducing plastics in the environment. The results show that the most effective consumer-based actions are for people to switch to: wooden cutlery; reusable water bottles; plastic free cotton-buds; wooden stirrers; and to refill shampoo bottles. If everyone in the UK switched to reusable items, such as water bottles, we could reduce plastic pollution in our rivers and ocean by nearly 25,000 tonnes annually (Marazzi *et al.*, 2020). Through a parallel citizen science project we found that particularly bad habits are discarding empty food (e.g. wrappers) and drink containers (i.e. bottles) as well as cigarette butts and packaging in urban parks.

Though teenagers are often blamed for carelessly dropping their wrappers or bottles anywhere, but in the right bin (but see what [movement two young sisters built!](#)), we can all do better. Plastic can be reduced in our laboratories: plastic mono-use tips, culture flasks, pipettes, can often be readily substituted with glass. And the current, persistent

Fig. 1 The most prevalent plastic items found by Winton *et al.* (2020).

COVID-19 pandemic, is causing plastic litter to increase because people drop, intentionally or not, disposable / single-use face masks and gloves in the streets. No littering is justifiable and, as responsible citizens, we are all called to 'go the extra-mile' by taking our litter home from parks, if bins are scarce and/or already full. But more structural solutions are needed. Groups of concerned residents and campaigning groups

Fig. 2 The customisable ashtrays ballot bins help reduce litter by 46%.

can (and do) contact local councils to urge them to (i) place more bins in key hotspots; (ii) place signs to urge people to avoid littering (iii) enforce fines on those who litter. Creative approaches such as ballot bins have shown promising results: smokers can discard cigarette butts whilst answering questions (e.g. "What is the best superpower: flying or invisibility?" or sports-related ones; Fig. 2).

Overall, people may find it hard to choose how to cut down on single-use plastics because they receive conflicting information on alternative products or appropriate choices. Science is so important because clear and accurate information is needed on the feasibility of different actions to reduce plastic use, incorrect disposal and thus pollution. Ultimately, environmentally sustainable actions need to become new norms and widely accepted habits, which means people have to stop denying their responsibility or the effects of their actions on wildlife in rivers, lakes, and the ocean.

So let's start with measuring how much and which plastics we use. You can complete this on-the-go plastic use survey and share it widely (>1,300

Your on-the-go plastic footprint

Welcome

Most of us use plastic items everyday but the majority of this ends up in our rivers and oceans, affecting wildlife and humans alike. According to the Ocean Conservancy, by 2050 there could be more plastic in the oceans than there are fish.

The complexity, scale and urgency of the plastics challenge means this is a problem we must tackle together.

Use our calculator to find out your on-the-go plastic footprint and how to reduce it. On-the-go plastic is the plastic you use out of the house.

LET'S BEGIN

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Fig. 3 Earthwatch Europe's plastic footprint calculator gathers key data on people's plastic use and actions to reduce it.

responses so far: Fig. 3); it also asks you to share what you are doing to reduce your plastic use and/or what obstacles you face in doing that.

Although, for plastic pollution and other phenomena, it is much better to 'close the tap' than 'mop the floor', some organisations are reclaiming plastics from the ocean to produce new plastic items. (e.g. The Ocean Cleanup and Plastic Bank). Plastics are useful and not always bad for the environment; think about how much lighter airplanes and cars are today than some decades ago and how paper bags are heavier so that their transportation emits more greenhouse gases. But too much plastics is bad, especially when not strictly necessary (in the UK, the average person uses 150 plastic bottles when carrying one's own reusable bottle costs way less!). The Refill campaign made so many new water points

available, so far saving 100 million bottles from ever being used. The global plastic pollution challenge can indeed be solved, with creativity and commitment by citizens, businesses, NGOs, and governments. As virgin plastics is produced from fossil fuels, a more sober plastic use and alternative options will reduce greenhouse gas emissions, thus supporting climate change mitigation. Less single-use plastics around will ultimately help humans as well as freshwater fish, sea turtles, and marine mammals and birds.

Acknowledgments

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References

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